

Synthesis of 1:2:7-Trihydroxy-5-methylanthrone- 8-carboxylic Acid.

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In course of oxidation of coccine (*Annalen*, 1916, 399, 1) the polyhydric phenol residue is lost, with the production of cochenillic acid, to which the following constitution has been assigned by Dimroth from analytical standpoint and some of the reactions of the acid.

It was therefore of some interest to attempt synthesis of anthrones composed of a *m*-cresotinic acid residue and a polyhydric phenol residue, which on oxidation may possibly produce cochenillic acid and thus definitely settle its constitution.

With this end in view 3:4:5-trimethoxy-1:2-phthalide (Alimchandani and Meldrum, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 964), 6-methyl-3:5-dimethoxy-1:2-phthalide (Mitter, Sen and Paul, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 536) and 5:6-dimethoxy-1:2 phthalide (meconine) were condensed with ethyl methoxy-*m*-cresotinate in presence of aluminium chloride (King, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 563) and partially demethylated benzylbenzoic acid derivatives were obtained. The yield of these condensation products, was generally low, and they hardly undergo ring closure to yield anthrone derivatives. Only a very poor yield of anthrone derivative could be obtained from the condensation product of meconine and ethyl methoxy-*m*-cresotinate which on demethylation with hydrobromic acid in glacial acetic acid gave the following compound.

(I)

The quantity of 1:2:7-trihydroxy-5-methylanthrone-8-carboxylic acid (I) obtained was very small and no more than 0.5 g. of the substance could be subjected to the oxidising action of alkaline hydrogen peroxide (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 1625) from which no definite result could be obtained and so the following alternative scheme for the synthesis of (I) was adopted.

Opianic acid was condensed with ethyl-*m*-cresotinate in presence of 85 per cent. sulphuric acid (Jacobson and Adam, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 2011). The condensation product was then hydrolysed with 10 per cent. alcoholic potash and the product of hydrolysis completely reduced with zinc dust and 10 per cent. caustic soda solution. The benzylbenzoic acid derivative thus produced may have the alternative formulae given below.

(II)

(III)

The neutral methoxymethyl ester was prepared and found to be identical with that prepared from the condensation product of meconine with ethyl methoxy-*m*-cresotinate, where condensation takes place mainly at the *para*-position to the OMe group of ethyl methoxy-*m*-cresotinate, as is evident from the ring closure of the benzylbenzoic acid derivative already mentioned. The identity of the benzylbenzoic acid derivatives prepared by alternative methods, leaves no room for doubt as to the constitution of the product being (II).

A proper condition for ring closure of (II) to yield anthrone derivative has not yet been found and all attempts to that end have so far failed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of meconine with ethyl methoxy-m-cresotinate.—Meconine (10 g.) and ethyl methoxy-*m*-cresotinate (10 g.) were dissolved in chloroform (50 c. c.) in a R. B. flask fitted up with a reflux condenser, and anhydrous aluminium chloride

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(10 g.) was added in two instalments and heated on the water-bath for 6 hours, when the reaction mixture turned into a deep brown homogeneous solution. A further quantity of aluminium chloride (15 g.) was then added and the heating continued for a further period of 20 hours. The reaction product was found to be deep red solid mass, which was then decomposed with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid and steam distilled to ensure the decomposition of the aluminium compound formed during the reaction. The reaction product was then cooled and extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed repeatedly with sodium bicarbonate solution. The bicarbonate-wash on acidification with hydrochloric acid yielded the condensation product as a brown solid, which crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m. p. 207°. [Found: C, 61.16; H, 5.22; OMe, 9.60. $C_{17}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 61.45; H, 4.82; OMe (Mono), 9.33 per cent.].

Neutral methoxymethyl ester of the above benzylbenzoic acid derivative was prepared by heating the same (1.5 g.) with sodium (0.5 g.) in methyl alcohol and methyl iodide (4 g.) in a sealed tube for 2 hours at 100°. It crystallised from methyl alcohol in stout needles, m. p. 98-99°. (Found: C, 64.57; H, 6.34. $C_{21}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 64.94; H, 6.18 per cent.).

Ring closure of the condensation product.—The condensation product was dissolved in chemically pure sulphuric acid (5 c.c.) to a deep red solution, and kept for 12 hours at ordinary temperature, when the colour of the solution changed to dirty green. It was then warmed at 65-70° for 10 minutes, when the colour changed, first from bottle green to deep green, then blue and ultimately bluish violet, when it was cooled and poured on to crushed ice. The solid reaction product which was black with a violet tinge was separated, dried and dissolved in ethyl acetate. The deep red ethyl acetate extract was made free from tarry impurities by precipitating them with petroleum ether, when a beautiful scarlet solution was obtained, which on concentration gave the reaction product as a pink powder. It crystallised from a large volume of benzene with a few drops of ethyl acetate in needles, m. p. 225°. (Found: C, 64.57; H, 5.0. $C_{17}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 64.97; H, 4.46 per cent.).

1:2:7-Trihydroxy-5-methylanthrone-8-carboxylic acid, (1).—The product of ring closure (1 g.) (m. p. 225°), as described above was demethylated by heating with hydrobromic acid in glacial acetic

acid (15 c.c.) under reflux for 3-4 hours. The acetic acid was removed from the reaction product under reduced pressure in a desiccator over caustic potash, when the compound was obtained mixed with some tarry matter, which was removed by fractional precipitation with benzene, from an ethyl acetate solution of the reaction product. The compound thus obtained was dissolved in least quantity of glacial acetic acid and allowed to stand in a desiccator over caustic potash when it was obtained in crystalline condition, m. p. 255° (decomp.) with previous blackening between 245-50°. It dissolves in alkali with a violet coloration which changes ultimately to deep brown. (Found : C, 63.84; H, 4.25. $C_{16}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 64.0; H, 4.0 per cent.).

Condensation of opianic acid with ethyl m-cresotinate.—Opianic acid (14 g.) was intimately mixed with ethyl *m*-cresotinate (12 g.) and to the mixture sulphuric acid (85 p. c., 40 c.c.) was added, when a light brown homogeneous solution resulted with slight rise in temperature. It was then allowed to stand at ordinary temperature for 6-7 hours and diluted with water, when the condensation product separated. It was then extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried with calcium chloride and ether allowed to evaporate when the reaction product was obtained as a solid, crystallising from alcohol in needles, m. p. 93°. (Found: C, 64.71; H, 5.71. $C_{20}H_{20}O_7$ requires C, 64.52; H, 5.38 per cent.).

The corresponding acid was obtained by hydrolysing the condensation product by heating with 5 times the required quantity of alcoholic potash under reflux on a water-bath for 3 hours. The reaction mixture was then diluted with half its volume of water, alcohol driven off on a water-bath, cooled and acidified with hydrochloric acid, when a white solid separated. It crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 255°. (Found: C, 62.44; H, 4.9. $C_{18}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 62.79; H, 4.65 per cent.).

The same compound was obtained by direct condensation of opianic acid with *m*-cresotinic acid in presence of 85 p. c. sulphuric acid but it is not advantageous owing to the difficulty of separation of the required condensation product from the unreacted acids.

Benzylbenzoic acid derivative, (II).—The reduction of the preceding compound (m. p. 255°) to the corresponding benzylbenzoic acid derivative was achieved by boiling the same (10 g.) with fresh zinc dust (30 g.) and caustic soda solution (10 p. c., 200 c.c.) under

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vigorous mechanical stirring under reflux for 20 hours. When the reaction was over, the reaction mixture was cooled and filtered, the filtrate on acidification with hydrochloric acid gave the reduction product as a pasty mass, which soon solidified. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid in prisms, m. p. 183°. (Found: C, 62.05; H, 5.52. $C_{18}H_{18}O_7$ requires C, 62.43; H, 5.2 per cent.).

A neutral methoxymethyl ester of the benzylbenzoic acid derivative (m. p. 183°) was prepared in a similar way as that of the condensation product of meconine with ethyl methoxy-*m*-cresotinate. It crystallised from methyl alcohol, m. p. 101°. (Found: C, 64.82; H, 6.45. $C_{21}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 64.94; H, 6.18 per cent.). The identity of the two neutral methoxymethyl esters was ensured by an observation of no depression in the melting point of an intimate mixture of the two.

*Condensation of 3:4:5-trimethoxy-1:2-phthalide with ethyl methoxy-*m*-cresotinate.*—Equimolecular quantities of 3:4:5-trimethoxy-1:2-phthalide and ethyl methoxy-*m*-cresotinate in chloroform solution were treated with aluminium chloride, the procedure being the same as that used in the case of the condensation of meconine with ethyl methoxy-*m*-cresotinate. The compound crystallised in beautiful needles from benzene, m. p. 137°. (Found: C, 59.27; H, 5.11. $C_{18}H_{18}O_8$ requires C, 59.68; H, 4.97 per cent.).

*Condensation of 6-methyl-3:5 dimethoxy-1:2-phthalide with ethyl methoxy-*m*-cresotinate.*—The condensation of equimolecular quantity of the phthalide and ethyl methoxy-*m*-cresotinate was carried out in chloroform solution in presence of aluminium chloride as usual, only the heating on the water-bath was prolonged to 35 hours. The substance crystallised from water with a little alcohol in beautiful white stout needles, m. p. 203.04°. (Found: C, 62.62; H, 5.68. $C_{18}H_{18}O_7$ requires C, 62.43; H, 5.2 per cent.).

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